

Religiosity, Sexual Shame and Purity Beliefs between Early and Late Adult Women

Saranya Srivastava and Seema Rani Sarraf

Amity Institute of Behaviour and Allied Science (AIBAS), Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow Campus, Uttar Pradesh

The present study examines the relation between religiosity and sexual shame, with the mediating effect of purity beliefs, through a correlational analysis in adult women of an urban setting. The study further comprises a comparative analysis, assessing age differences in the measure of religiosity, sexual shame and purity beliefs between early adult women (<30 years) and later adult women (>30 years). The sample consisted of 120 urban women, collected through convenience sampling. Religiosity was measured by the Centrality of Religiosity scale (Huber & Huber, 2012), purity beliefs were measured through the Purity Culture Beliefs Scale (Ortiz, 2018) and sexual shame was measured by the Sexual Shame Inventory (Seebeck, 2021). Pearson correlational analysis showcased that religiosity was significantly positively associated with purity values, and purity values were significantly positively related to sexual shame. Though religiosity was revealed to have an insignificant negative correlation with sexual shame. These findings indicate an indirect relation between religiosity and sexual shame through the internalization of purity beliefs regarding women sexuality. Further, One-way ANOVA revealed that later adult women showcased significantly higher levels of religiosity and purity beliefs than early adult women, but an insignificant difference was found in terms of sexual shame, suggesting feeling of sexual shame in women may go beyond the interaction of purity beliefs with religiosity.

Keywords: Religiosity, sexual shame, purity values, adult women, urban setting

One of the pioneers in the psychology of religion, Gordan Allport along with Micheal Ross précised the concept of personal religious orientation, assessing it to be an individually unique approach towards faith, dimensioning it to be either intrinsic, an end in itself an internalized motive relating to a mature form of religion or extrinsic, a means to an end a tool for social status and self-assurance relating to an immature form of religion (Allport, 1950; Allport & Ross, 1967). Where the early empirical view towards religiosity is rooted in attendance and membership in religious practices, formulation of a dimensional view and a more innate prospect of religiousness began. Furthering the multidimensionality of religions, Charles Glock identified religion into five dimensions - intellectual, ideological, ritualistic, experimental, and consequential (Glock, 1962) later dividing ritualistic into separate dimensions - private practice and public practice and removing the consequential one, in a revision (Stark & Glock, 1968; Glock, 1973). Rooted in Glock's multidimensional model, Huber, whose measure, the Centrality of Religiosity Scale (Huber & Huber, 2012) is used in the current study, expressed religiosity as the extent of importance religious meaning

holds to one's personality, extending to varying ends as a means to; overall, how central religious meaning is to an individual. Identifying the lack of trans religious generalization in the model by Glock (1968) having a Christian bias, a more universal approach was taken for the measure of religiosity. A revised five dimensions of religiosity were furthered, entailing five dimensions as of intellectual, ideology, public practice, private practice, and religious experience as personal religious construct corresponding to an individual's held religious meaning (Huber, 2003, 2006, 2007).

Sexuality, conceptualized early by Freud (1905) is through Libido a sexual drive acting as a primary force behind human motivation. Aligning with the psychosexual stages of fixations (Freud, 1915), sexuality formulation was associated with the unconscious identification towards the parental figure (Freud, 1931). Sexuality now is taken as a uniquely shaped set of experiences and behaviour in individuals, existing on a spectrum, largely supported by Kinsey (1948, 1953) who shifted the understanding of sexuality from early views leaning towards moral interpretations or association to deviances towards the lens of actual observed sexual behaviour. Shame in general, along with guilt, a term following closely, are labelled as "self-conscious emotions" (Tangney & Fischer, 1995) which unlike basic emotions, is developed through judgement of oneself on the premise of good or bad, right or wrong on standards of morality (Tangney & Salovey, 2010) and hence are experienced on behaviour condemned socially or personally (Lewis et al., 1989; Eisenberg, 2000; Cohen et al., 2011; Lewis, 1992). Sexual shame, a negative evaluation aligning to feeling of shame and to one's sexuality (Gordon, 2017) predictably stems from past experiences; sexual abuse and trauma, sex, and socially devised views along internalized constructs regarding one's expression of sexuality, especially in women, on par with the ever-present patriarchy. Feminist theories (de Beauvoir, 2011; Bartky, 1990) suggest sexuality in women is largely conditioned by social factors including religion enforcing patriarchal order, how society is

Author Note

Saranya Srivastava, Amity Institute of Behaviour and Allied Science (AIBAS), Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow Campus Uttar Pradesh

Seema Rani Sarraf, Amity Institute of Behaviour and Allied Science (AIBAS), Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow Campus Uttar Pradesh

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Seema Rani Sarraf, Amity Institute of Behaviour and Allied Science (AIBAS), Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow Campus Uttar Pradesh

E-mail: srsarraf@lko.amity.edu

constructed to seconding women's expression to men's; framing them as the "other" along with how varying sociocultural factor contributes to the internalization of shame and inferiority to the point that harsh oppression is carried by women on themselves like a male witness would do to their conduct. Researches have often showed a double standard in nature where men are usually applauded (Ringrose & Harvey, 2015) or least criticized for the same behaviour a woman on average, would be violently condemned and stigmatized for (Crawford & Popp, 2003; Hamilton & Armstrong 2009; Endendijk et al., 2020) and hence the widespread orchestration of slut shaming for sexual behaviours as well as of expressions deduced to be; adding to sexual shame while self-enforcing behavioural regulation to fit the traditional binary (Burgess & Borgida, 1999; Butler, 2004). Further, women also enforce the same harsh judgement to other women as a form of internalized oppression (Clayton & Trafimow, 2007; Ringrose & Renold, 2012; Armstrong et al., 2014). Sexual shame in recent times, as a measured construct, though limited tools are present, is stated by Kyle (2013) as a feeling resulting from experience, causing beliefs of being flawed and unworthy of acceptance and belongingness regarding sexuality, which he based the Kyle Inventory of Sexual Shame (KISS) on this conceptualization. Furthered by Seebeck (2021) whose measure, the Sexual Shame Inventory (SSI), is used in the current study, operationalized sexual shame as a domain-specific construct, one existing under the general feeling of shame, about internalized (intrapersonal) sexual shame, relational (interpersonal) sexual shame and sexual inferiority.

The early conceptualization of purity is derived from anthropological studies, delving into social structures, rites, rituals and taboos. Early researchers (Durkheim, 2008; Frazer, 2009) establish the organization of society through religious involvement, separating it into two worlds - sacred and profane, where taboos, inducing feelings of shame and disgust were to keep the two separated. Purity rituals and taboos were further argued to be logically embedded structures (Douglas, 2002) one of boundaries, hierarchy, and social order to maintain the binaries of pure and impure, also supported through the implication of the Indian caste system, proposing the two at its foundation (Dumont, 1970). Purity shifted to today's moralized component of the psychological field, with the affective association of the otherwise to disgust, specifically due to how rooted it is to one's moral foundation and its high correlation to conservative values (Haidt & Joseph, 2007; Inbar et al., 2009). Disgust is further proposed to amplify the importance of maintaining morally fit constructs, ensuring one's pureness (Horberg et al., 2009). Recent studies focus on how purity overall tends to be an abstract term (Gray et al., 2023) along with how internalization of beliefs associated to it can affect interaction with varying constructs, with chastity and sexual regulation as a form of moral standard in adding to purity-based beliefs, further contributing to sexual shame (e.g., Coates et al., 2025; Thwaites, 2025).

As research aligning religiosity, sexual shame, and mediation of purity at present is limited demands to be variably explored in their dynamic engagement, specifically in an Indian context, along with the complexity of urban settings with constant exposure to liberating, modern views, along with the ever-continued influence of religion on women's lives. Therefore, the present study seeks to investigate the relationship between the key variables, as well as studying the differences among age groups, to further establish variances in the resulting relationship.

Method

Participants

The total sample consisted of 120 urban adult women (N=120), divided equally into 60 early adult women (≤ 30 years) and 60 later adult women (> 30 years). Data collection was done on a convenience sampling basis. Informed consent was maintained and participants were assured of confidentiality. In terms of religion, the majority of the sample identified as Hindu, with a total of 112 participants (93.33%), 5 participants identified as Muslim, and 3 were Christian.

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative, correlational research design along with a comparative one through the measure of Pearson's correlational coefficient and One-Way ANOVA, respectively.

Measures

The Centrality of Religiosity Scale-15 (Huber & Huber, 2012), a 15-item self-reporting scale, was used to measure personal constructs of religiosity through five dimensions: intellectual, ideological, public practice, private practice and religious experience. Each dimension consists of three items. The scale measured responses on a 5-point Likert Scale ranging from 1 (*least religious centrality*) to 5 (*highest religious centrality*). The higher the score, the higher religious personal constructs are central to the individual. In three studies, the reliabilities ranged from 0.92 to 0.96 for the whole CRS-15.

The Purity Culture Beliefs Scale (Ortiz, 2018), a 24-item scale was used to measure purity beliefs regarding sexuality. The scale comprised items of 3 components along with a control one as follows: shame and guilt (7 items), gender roles (6 items), idealization (7 items) and control (4 items). The component of control item being Christian beliefs about sexuality, made for the purpose of the original study was not included as it was deemed unreliable in its original construction. It also couldn't align with the context of an Indian population used in the current study. The tool measured responses on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*Strongly disagree*) to 5 (*Strongly agree*). Higher scores represent higher purity-based beliefs regarding sexuality. The reliability of the scale was examined through internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha in the original study. The results indicated high reliability for the overall scale, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.90.

The Sexual Shame Inventory (Seebeck, 2021), a 10-item self-reporting scale was used to measure sexual shame, comprising 3 subscales: sexual inferiority (3 items), relational sexual shame (4 items) and internalized sexual shame (3 items). The SSI measured responses on 6-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*Strongly Disagree*) to 6 (*Strongly Agree*). Higher score indicates a higher level of sexual shame. For the reliability of the SSI, internal consistency was examined using Cronbach's alpha coefficient in the original study. The results indicated high reliability for the overall scale, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.86.

Procedure

All measures were combined into a structured booklet, administered on a one-on-one basis. Data collection was done on a convenience sampling basis. Willing participants were screened through the inclusion criteria of being an adult woman in an urban setting. Informed consent was maintained and participants were assured of

confidentiality. The data collected was then analyzed using statistical software.

Results

Descriptive statistics and One- way ANOVA (Table 1) were calculated to see the group effect on religiosity, purity culture belief and sexual shame.

The resulting statistics (Table 1) showed a significant difference in religiosity (all domains), purity beliefs (all domains) and relational sexual shame (domain of sexual shame) between the early and later groups.

Table 2 explains the correlation between religiosity (CRS-15) and purity values (PCBS).

Table 1

Mean ± Standard Deviation and One-Way ANOVA Across Age Groups (N = 120)

Measure		Early Adult (Mean ± SD)	Later Adult (Mean ± SD)	F value (1,118)
Centrality of Religiosity Scale	Intellectual	10.03 ± 2.89	11.28 ± 2.89	5.609*
	Ideology	10.85 ± 3.24	12.70 ± 2.37	12.750*
	Public Practice	9.55 ± 3.35	11.37 ± 2.82	10.314*
	Private Practice	10.95 ± 3.64	13.05 ± 1.94	15.554*
	Religious Experience	9.98 ± 3.38	11.93 ± 2.38	13.345*
	Total CRS	52.83 ± 12.24	58.17 ± 9.40	7.164*
Purity Culture Beliefs Scale (PCBS)	Shame & Guilt	15.20 ± 4.91	19.82 ± 6.41	19.594*
	Idealization	14.95 ± 5.65	19.75 ± 6.77	17.777*
Sexual Shame Inventory (SSI)	Gender Roles	11.00 ± 4.26	14.47 ± 5.45	15.081*
	Total PCBS	41.15 ± 13.35	54.03 ± 17.40	20.704*
	Relational Sexual Shame	9.18 ± 4.26	11.05 ± 3.83	6.372*
Sexual Shame Inventory (SSI)	Sexual Inferiority	7.23 ± 3.54	7.63 ± 2.99	0.448
	Internalized Sexual Shame	7.08 ± 3.73	7.65 ± 3.82	0.676
	Total SSI	23.50 ± 10.03	26.33 ± 8.91	2.675

Note. * $p < .05$ indicates statistical significance.

Table 2

Correlations among CRS and PCBS

Measure	CRS-15					
	Intellectual	Ideology	Public Practice	Private Practice	Religious Experience	Total CRS
PCBS						
Shame & Guilt	.195*	.188*	.302**	.346**	.249**	.272**
Idealization	.286**	.266**	.398**	.440**	.362**	.329**
Gender Roles	.231*	.118	.319**	.281**	.196*	.293**
Total PCBS	.257**	.211*	.367**	.389**	.296**	.321**

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

From Table 2, we can see that individuals with higher centrality of religiosity were more likely to endorse stronger purity beliefs regarding sexuality.

The relationship between sexual shame and purity belief is presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Pearson Correlations among SSI and PCBS

Measure	SSI			
	Relational Sexual shame	Sexual Inferiority	Internalized sexual shame	Total SSI
PCBS				
Shame & Guilt	.258**	.189*	.243**	.272**
Idealization	.300**	.216*	.347**	.341**
Gender Roles	.405**	.313**	.381**	.433**
Total PCBS	.339**	.252**	.345**	.369**

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

The results from Table 3 showed that purity beliefs (PCBS) and sexual shame (SSI) have a significant positive correlation, which indicates that women who internalise stronger purity beliefs

regarding sexuality report higher levels of sexual shame.

The relation between sexual shame and religiosity is being discussed in Table 4.

Table 4
Correlations between CRS-15 and SSI

Measures	SSI			
	Sexual Shame	Sexual Inferiority	Internalized Shame	Total SSI
CRS- 15				
Intellectual	-.009	.071	.120	.068
Ideology	-.030	-.078	.049	-.020
Public Practice	.133	.126	.201*	.180*
Private Practice	.112	.029	.127	.109
Religious Experience	.076	-.015	.172	.096
Total CRS	-.049	-.007	.046	-.005

Note. * $p < .05$. Non-significant values shown without markers.

The result of Pearson correlation analysis conducted to examine direct associations between religiosity (CRS-15) and sexual shame (SSI) dimensions showed a non-significant negative correlation between religiosity and sexual shame in the present study.

Discussion

The present study showed a significant positive correlation between religiosity (CRS-15) and purity beliefs regarding sexuality (PCBS), indicating that religious socialization often promotes purity-based ideals, particularly for women, where sexuality is regulated through moral frameworks tied to virtue and character (Coates et al., 2025; Thwaites, 2025). Further, the strong association between the idealization dimension of purity beliefs and all dimensions of religiosity suggests that greater centrality of religion contributes to the internalization of idealized standards of sexual purity; aligning with moral foundations theory, which posits that purity is a key moral domain linked to religiosity and conservative values (Haidt & Joseph, 2007; Inbar et al., 2009).

The present study found that purity beliefs (PCBS) had a significant positive correlation with sexual shame (SSI). The shame and guilt dimension of the PCBS showed a strong association with relational sexual shame and internalized sexual shame from the SSI. Idealization dimension (PCBS) was also positively related to both forms of sexual shame (SSI), and the gender-roles dimension (PCBS) showed the strongest links with all dimensions of sexual shame (SSI). This pattern suggests that purity beliefs function as a moral framework through which women's sexuality is evaluated, with chastity, modesty, and gendered expectations contributing to shame. This interpretation is consistent with recent work showing that purity messages position women's sexual worth around sexual restraint and that exposure to purity-culture beliefs is associated with elevated sexual shame and internalized stigma (Pugh, 2025). Coates et al. (2025) found that women who were exposed to strong purity messages in childhood showed significantly higher sexual shame as adults. In this view, a woman's worth is tied to her sexual purity (Ortiz, 2018). It also aligns with prior research indicating that religiosity and related sexual moral beliefs are linked to sex guilt, conservative sexual attitudes, and lower sexual self-esteem in women (Abbott et al., 2016; Murray et al., 2007; Woo et al., 2012).

The findings of the present study showed a non-significant negative correlation between total religiosity (CRS-15) and total sexual shame (SSI), indicating no meaningful direct association between the two variables in this sample. This suggests that religiosity may not directly relate to sexual shame, and instead influences it indirectly through the internalization of purity beliefs and the moral regulation of sexuality. Prior studies have shown that religiosity is often linked to sexual outcomes through guilt, attitudes, and internalized moral standards rather than through a simple direct effect (Brooks & Weitzman, 2022; Murray et al., 2007; Woo et al., 2012). In women, religious commitment has also been associated with more conservative sexual attitudes and lower sexual self-esteem, further suggesting that the emotional impact of religiosity is often mediated by internalized beliefs rather than religiosity alone (Abbott et al., 2016).

The findings of the present study revealed significant age-related differences in religiosity and purity beliefs, with later adult women (>30 years) scoring significantly higher than early adult women (≤ 30 years) across all dimensions of both measures. This suggests that religiosity and the internalisation of purity-based moral beliefs tend to strengthen with age, possibly reflecting religious socialisation and the deeper embedding of traditional values over time. Prior research supports this pattern, indicating that religiosity generally increases with age and is associated with greater endorsement of conservative moral attitudes, including those related to sexuality and gender roles (Argue et al., 1999; Koenig, 2012). Studies have also shown that older individuals are more likely to internalise traditional sexual norms and purity-based expectations compared to younger cohorts, who may be more influenced by contemporary, liberal perspectives on sexuality (Marcinechová & Záhorcová, 2020).

In contrast, the results indicated no significant difference between early and later adult women in overall sexual shame, suggesting that sexual shame may be influenced by a broader range of sociocultural and psychological factors beyond age (Fahs, 2014; Woo et al., 2012). In contemporary urban contexts, younger women may experience sexual shame through exposure to conflicting norms, liberal sexual attitudes with internalised traditional expectations, while older women may reflect more stable but internalised moral frameworks, suggesting the findings.

Limitations of the Study

The limitations about the present study include the use of convenience sampling. The sample population was restricted to women in an urban setting. Regression-based predictive analysis was not conducted. Given the sensitive content and the urban setting, participants with a liberal, modern view were predictively more present, limiting the scope of the study.

Further Directions and Implications of the Study

More research in this direction could strengthen the understanding of the relationship between religiosity and sexual shame, as the indirect relation could be further approached with the mediation of purity beliefs. More studies could be undertaken, entailing participation from rural and semiurban settings, along with people of varying religions as studies on the Indian population are limited. Use of a more probabilistic sampling can help derive a more variable and generalisable result. Further, regression-based studies could be undertaken to determine predictive analysis and an in-depth assessment of the mediating variable of purity belief.

Conclusion

The study provides evidence that religiosity is strongly associated with purity beliefs; further providing that purity beliefs showcased a strong relationship with sexual shame, though no direct relation between religiosity and sexual shame is found. These findings suggest a more indirect relation between religiosity and sexual shame with the mediation of purity beliefs. In the comparative aspect, age differences were significantly present among all dimensions of religiosity and purity beliefs, but none were found in the context of sexual shame in urban adult women, suggesting internalization of sexual shame beyond purity beliefs and religiosity.

References

- Abbott, D. M., Harris, J. E., & Mollen, D. (2016). The impact of religious commitment on women's sexual self-esteem. *Sexuality and Culture*, 20(4), 1063-1082.
- Allport, G. W. (1950). *The individual and his religion*. New York, NY: Macmillan.
- Allport, G. W., & Ross, M. J. (1967). Personal religious orientation and prejudice. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 5(4), 432-443. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0021212>
- Argue, A., Johnson, D. R., & White, L. K. (1999). Age and religiosity: Evidence from a three-wave panel analysis. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 38(3), 423-435.
- Armstrong, E. A., Hamilton, L. T., Armstrong, E. M., & Seeley, J. L. (2014). "Good girls": Gender, social class, and slut discourse on campus. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 77(2), 100-122. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0190272514521220>
- Arcinechová, D., & Zahorcová, K. (2020). Sexual shame and sexual satisfaction in intimate relationships: The mediating role of sexual communication. *Sexual and Relationship Therapy*, 35(4), 509-523. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681994.2019.1659967>
- Bartky, S. L. (1990). *Femininity and domination: Studies in the phenomenology of oppression*. Routledge.
- Brooks, I. H. M., & Weitzman, A. (2022). Religiosity and young unmarried women's sexual and contraceptive behavior: New evidence from a longitudinal panel of young adult women. *Demography*, 59(3), 895-920.
- Burgess, D., & Borgida, E. (1999). Who women are, who women should be: Descriptive and prescriptive gender stereotyping in sex discrimination. *Psychology, Public Policy, and Law*, 5(3), 665-692. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1076-8971.5.3.665>
- Butler, J. (2004). *Undoing gender*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Clayton, K. D., & Trafimow, D. (2007). A test of three hypotheses concerning attributions toward female promiscuity. *The Social Science Journal*, 44(4), 677-686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sosocij.2007.10.003>
- Coates, A. G., Metcalfe, K., Ensign, A., Abdalla, S., & Meston, C. (2025). Being pure and being ashamed: The role of purity culture in sexual well-being. *The Journal of Sexual Medicine*, 22(Suppl. 1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jsxmed/qdaf068.049>
- Cohen, T. R., Wolf, S. T., Panter, A. T., & Insko, C. A. (2011). Introducing the GASP scale: A new measure of guilt and shame proneness. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 100(5), 947-966. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0022641>
- de Beauvoir, S. (1953). *The second sex* (H. M. Parshley, Trans.). New York, NY: Alfred A. Knopf. (Original work published 1949.)
- Douglas, M. (2002). *Purity and danger: An analysis of concepts of pollution and taboo*. Routledge. (Original work published 1966).
- Dumont, L. (1970). *Homo hierarchicus: The caste system and its implications* (M. Sainsbury, Trans.). Weidenfeld & Nicolson.
- Durkheim, É. (2008). *The elementary forms of religious life* (C. Cosman, Trans.). Oxford, England: Oxford University Press. (Original work published in 1912.)
- Eisenberg, N. (2000). Emotion, regulation, and moral development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 51, 665-697. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.51.1.665>
- Endendijk, J. J., van Baar, A. L., & Deković, M. (2020). He is a stud, she is a slut! A meta-analysis on the continued existence of sexual double standards. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 24(2), 163-190. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868319891310>
- Fahs, B. (2014). Coming to power: Women's fake orgasms and best orgasm experiences illuminate the failures of (hetero)sex and the pleasures of connection. *Culture, Health and Sexuality*, 16(8), 974-988.
- Fischer, K. W., & Tangney, J. P. (1995). Self-conscious emotions and the affect revolution: Framework and overview. In J. P. Tangney and K. W. Fischer (Eds.), *Self-conscious emotions: The psychology of shame, guilt, embarrassment, and pride* (pp. 3-22). Guilford Press.
- Frazer, J. G. (2009). *The golden bough: A study in magic and religion*. Oxford University Press. (Original work published 1890).
- Freud, S. (1905/1953). Three essays on the theory of sexuality (J. Strachey, Trans.). In J. Strachey (Ed.), *The standard edition of the complete psychological works of Sigmund Freud* (Vol. 7, pp. 123-246). London, England: Hogarth Press.
- Freud, S. (1915/1957). Instincts and their vicissitudes. In J. Strachey (Ed.), *The standard edition of the complete psychological works of Sigmund Freud* (Vol. 14, pp. 109-140). London, England: Hogarth Press.
- Freud, S. (1931/1953). Female sexuality. In J. Strachey (Ed.), *The standard edition of the complete psychological works of Sigmund Freud* (Vol. 21, pp. 225-243). London, England: Hogarth Press.
- Glock, C. Y. (1962). On the study of religious commitment. *Religious Education*, 57(Suppl. 4), S98-S110.
- Glock, C. Y. (1973). *Religion in sociological perspective: Essays in the empirical study of religion*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- Gordon, A. M. (2018). How men experience sexual shame: The development and validation of the Male Sexual Shame Scale. *Journal of Men's Studies*, 26(1), 105-123. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1060826517728303>
- Gray, K., DiMaggio, N., Schein, C., & Kachanoff, F. (2023). The problem of purity in moral psychology. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 27(3), 272-308. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10888683221124741>
- Haidt, J., & Joseph, C. (2007). The moral mind: How five sets of innate intuitions guide the development of many culture-specific virtues, and perhaps even modules. In P. Carruthers, S. Laurence, and S. P. Stich (Eds.), *The innate mind* (Vol. 3, pp. 367-391). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780195332827.003.0019>
- Hamilton, L., & Armstrong, E. A. (2009). Gendered sexuality in young adulthood: Double binds and flawed options. *Gender and Society*, 23(5), 589-616. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243209345829>
- Horberg, E. J., Oveis, C., Keltner, D., & Cohen, A. B. (2009). Disgust and the moralization of purity. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 97(6), 963-976. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017423>
- Huber, S. (2003). *Zeitlebens religiös? Die Persönlichkeit und ihr religiöses Konstruktssystem*. Regensburg: University of Regensburg.
- Huber, S. (2006). *Habitualized and internalized religion: The centrality of religiosity scale (CRS)*. Paper presented at the conference of the International Association for the Psychology of Religion, Leuven.
- Huber, S. (2007). "Anti-freud" or "Pro-Allport"? In *Psychology of Religion and Spirituality*.
- Huber, S., & Huber, O. W. (2012). The Centrality of Religiosity Scale (CRS). *Religions*, 3(3), 710-724. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel3030710>
- Inbar, Y., Pizarro, D. A., & Bloom, P. (2009). Conservatives are more easily disgusted than liberals. *Cognition and Emotion*, 23(4), 714-725. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699930802110007>
- Kaplan, R. M. (2025). Health psychology at a crossroads: Opportunities and challenges for the next decade. *Health Psychology*, 44(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0001300>
- Kinsey, A. C., Pomeroy, W. B., & Martin, C. E. (1948). *Sexual behavior in the human male*. Philadelphia, PA: W. B. Saunders.
- Kinsey, A. C., Pomeroy, W. B., Martin, C. E., & Gebhard, P. H. (1953). *Sexual behavior in the human female*. Philadelphia, PA: W. B. Saunders.

- Koenig, H. G. (2012). Religion, spirituality, and health: The research and clinical implications. *ISRN Psychiatry*, 2012, 133. <https://doi.org/10.5402/2012/278730>
- Kyle, S. E. (2013). *Identification and treatment of sexual shame: Development of a measurement tool and group therapy protocol*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation) American Academy of Clinical Sexologists, San Antonio, TX.
- Lewis, M. (1992). *Shame: The exposed self*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Lewis, M., Sullivan, M. W., Stanger, C., & Weiss, M. (1989). Self-development and self-conscious emotions. *Child Development*, 60(1), 146-156.
- Litam, S. A., & Speciale, M. (2021). Deconstructing sexual shame: Implications for clinical counselors and counselor educators. *Journal of Counseling Sexology and Sexual Wellness: Research, Practice, and Education*, 3(1), 14-24. <https://doi.org/10.34296/03011045>
- Murray, S. L., Holmes, J. G., & Griffin, D. W. (2007). Self-esteem and the quest for felt security: How perceived regard regulates attachment processes. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 92(3), 425-440. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.92.3.425>
- Ortiz, A. M. (2018). *Developing a measure of purity culture: Sexual messages in evangelical Christian culture* (Doctoral dissertation, Biola University). ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Pugh, M.J. (2025). *Evaluating U.S. purity culture's impact on female sexual health and development* (Master's thesis, Kansas State University).
- Ringrose, J., & Harvey, L. (2015). Boobs, back-off, six packs and bits: Mediated body parts, gendered reward, and sexual shame in teens' sexting images. *Continuum*, 29(2), 205-217.
- Ringrose, J., & Renold, E. (2012). Slut-shaming, girl power and 'sexualisation': Thinking through the politics of the international SlutWalks with teen girls. *Gender and Education*, 24(3), 333-343.
- Seebeck, J. (2021). *Development of the Sexual Shame Inventory* (Doctoral dissertation, Seattle Pacific University).
- Stark, R., & Glock, C. Y. (1968). *American piety: The nature of religious commitment*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Thwaites, R., Churchard, A., Mofrad, L., Wood, D., & Brooks-Ucheaga, M. (2025). Considering the whole self: Integrating identity(s), context and power into the declarative procedural reflective (DPR) model of CBT practitioner development. *The Cognitive Behaviour Therapist*, 18, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1754470X25100135>
- Woo, J. S. T., Morshedian, N., Brotto, L. A., & Gorzalka, B. B. (2012). Sex guilt mediates the relationship between religiosity and sexual desire in East Asian and Euro-Canadian college-aged women. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 41(6), 1485-1495.

Received February 17, 2026

Revision received March 7, 2026

Accepted March 10, 2026